

PHILOSOPHICAL THEMES IN EMILY DICKINSON'S POETRY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7437638>

Abstract. *The emergence of poetry goes back long years. Until now, many poets create their own way of writing and enriching the pages of literature with their unrepeatably works. One of the owners of such abilities is Emily Dickinson. The purpose of this article is to reflect on the specific themes used in Emily Dickinson's poems. In her poems skillfully used themes of love, death, family, nature and religion.*

Keywords: *Emily Dickinson, love, death, nature, religion, poetry.*

ФИЛОСОФСКИЕ ТЕМЫ В ПОЭЗИИ ЭМИЛИ ДИКНСОН

Аннотация. *Возникновение поэзии насчитывает долгие годы. До сих пор многие поэты создают свой способ письма и обогащают страницы литературы своими неповторимыми произведениями. Одной из обладательниц таких способностей является Эмили Дикинсон. Цель этой статьи — поразмышлять над конкретными темами, использованными в стихах Эмили Дикинсон. В своих стихах умело использовала темы любви, смерти, семьи, природы и религии.*

Ключевые слова: *Эмили Дикинсон, любовь, смерть, природа, религия, поэзия.*

One of the most well-known poets of the 19th century was Emily Dickinson. Not only her poems considered valuable pieces of literature, she also helped advance the place of female writers. She famous for her unique poetry. Emily Dickinson wrote according to her life experience, the deepest thoughts and feelings. As a poet she deals with different themes like love, death, nature, religion, family and so on. Thus, the range of themes in her poetry is very various. She enriched her poems with such attractive, make readers think over and notable themes. Emily Dickinson was born on December 10, 1830 in Amherst, Massachusetts. She spent her entire adult life at her parent's home and never married. Her family was relatively prominent as they were responsible for the establishment of Amherst Collage, specifically her grandfather. While she was alive her friends and family knew she wrote poems but she did not publish many. Dickson's poems were published after her death. She was clearly curious about the outside world. Imaginative escape is one of the biggest aspects of her writing and the world she lived in, and is commonly reflects in various different themes. She wrote subjectively using all of the experience she could create in her mind.

Dickinson described death as one of the most crucial moments in life and she had a very calm approach to the subject. Therefore, she made it a common theme among her poetry. And it was reflected in many ways. Sometimes she personified it, and sometimes she afraid of it, and sometimes she faced it with challenge. In a large number of her poems she associates death with a horse driven carriage which symbolizes death. Dickinson was incorrigibly involved with serious discussions about life and death. "Death, and the problem of life after death, obsessed her. She seems to have thought of it constantly" (1, 162).

Besides being concerned with the death Dickinson composed numerable love poems. Love is the most recurring emotional theme in Emily Dickinson's poetry. Dickinson examines the idea of love from several angles, going at once personal and universal dimensions to her expressions. Love is a powerful liberating force which helps the soul to enjoy the bliss of life.

Dickinson's love poems are full of illuminating love passions and she often sings about love-dreams, flowers, love letters, surrounding of the lover and the beloved, bridal gown etc. Emily Dickinson's treatment of love shows her as a representative figure in the field of love and emotion. Her love poems are psychological as well as autobiographical. Love is a mystic life force it should be free from sensuous.

Emily Dickinson is a popular poet of nature. She paints nature on the canvas of solitude. Unlike most of the poets of her era, Dickinson was not under the influence of big romanticists such as Shelley or Wordsworth. She uses nature to practice human love which gives her poetry a rare aroma. Emily Dickinson's nature poems includes nature in different forms and aspects. She wrote about flies, butterflies, insects, birds, violent and power of nature such as winds, rain, thunderstorms, lightening, drought and earthquakes. The most notable elements of nature as the moon, the sun, the sea, the sky, the clouds, the rivers, the mountains and all fascinated her. The natural phenomenon like seasons, mornings, evening, dawn, dusk, sunrise, sunset, aurora, eclipse get prominence in her nature poems and they reflect an appropriate change that happens in nature. She takes different attitudes towards nature. Chase is of the view that for Emily Dickinson "Nature is aggressively a fact so consequential and inclusive a fact that it symbolizes itself" (2, 166). Nature remains a mystery for her. She has her own vision of nature. In some of her poems, she described nature as a source of pleasure and joy.

Religion is another essential element influenced to the Emily Dickinson's poetry. She was a religious person; religion is brought up many times in her poems. She speaks of God and Heaven in many of her poems. Some of her poems that include religious aspects are: "God permits industrious angels", "Going to Heaven!", "I went to Heaven", and "Bless God, he went as soldiers" (3,45). Dickinson's poems are able to illuminate religious and theological difficulties even as those difficulties often seem intensely relevant to her own poetic identity and quest and this is because she understood poetics to be engaged in a similar kind of epistemological enterprise as religious modes of thinking.

Dickinson's family made a huge impact in her writing. She also was confined to her house most of her life, so her poetry reflects the loneliness she experienced. Some of her poetry that shows the theme of her home life and loneliness is "I felt a funeral in my brain", "It was not death, for I stood up", and "There's a certain slant of life" (5,132).

In conclusion, Emily Dickinson's poetry shows her personal confession through better experience. Then we can call her greatest as a modern poet. Emily Dickinson is totally a perfect poet who express her deepest thoughts under the guise of various themes. This is reflected in how she deals with all of her other themes. Her poems come back to these central themes again and again, but they are never treated in exactly the same way. She discovers new sides to each of them.

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